

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-8-sep-2014>

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EARNINGS AND PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF GENERAL INSURANCE COMPANIES IN INDIA

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to analyse the performance of public sector insurance companies in India through the earning and profitability analyses. The four major PSUs currently operating in the Indian general insurance market are National, Oriental, United India and New India insurance companies. In practice, the Public Sector Units tend to focus their efforts on maintaining a strong status and market position within their local region rather than competing with one another. Although New India is generally regarded as the most successful of the public sector insurers. With an annual growth rate of 15-20% and the largest number of life insurance policies in force, the potential of the Indian insurance industry is huge. The National and Oriental insurance companies have witnessed increasing trend in ratio ranging between 193.07 & 248.93 and 132.83 & 155.39 respectively, while as for United and New India insurers, the capital adequacy ratio has witnessed decreasing trend is ranging between 106.56 & 83.38 and 87.28 & 69 respectively.

Key Words: Companies, Insurance, Performance, Profitability, Public Sector.

Introduction

The business of insurance is related to the protection of economic values of assets. Every asset has a value. The asset would have been created through the efforts of the owner. The asset is valuable to the owner, because he expects to get some benefit from it. It is a benefit because it meets some of his needs. The benefit may be an income or in some other form. In the case of a factory or a cow, the product generated by it is sold and income is generated. In the case of a motor car, it provides comfort and convenience in transportation. There is no direct income. Both are assets and provide benefits. After that,

the benefit may not be available. There is a life-time for a machine in a factory or a cow or a motor car. None of them will last forever. The owner is aware of this and he can so manage his affairs that by the end of the period or life-time, a substitute is made available. Thus, he makes sure that the benefit is not lost. However, the asset may get lost earlier. An accident or some other unfortunate event may destroy it or make it incapable of giving the benefits. The insurance sector is sine-quo-non for development and economic growth of any economy and it has been recognized for many years.

The Indian insurance market has been dominated by public sector companies, which have over a period of time, built up a national presence and a strong business franchise. The operating and financial position of these general insurance companies has been characterized by huge underwriting losses, substantially underutilized underwriting capacities, inadequate capitalization, combined reinsurance arrangements and sizeable investment portfolios. In a deregulated environment, it was expected that the available underwriting capacities and strong financial positions of these nationalized players will enable them to maintain their dominant positions even as competitive pressures would affect their growth rates and business acquisition costs. The low penetration of insurance products in the country, particularly in retail lines of business, present significant opportunities for the public sector insurers to launch innovative products and market them through their established distribution channels. However, monopolization of the insurance sector by the nationalized companies and their limited focus on retail business has prevented the Indian non-life insurance market from achieving its full growth potential. The risks underwritten by an insurance company are usually covered under fire, marine and miscellaneous portfolios, while the fire and marine portfolios primarily cover corporate risks, the miscellaneous portfolio covers the motor, third party and own damage, engineering, aviation, health and other retail classes of risk. The underwriting performance of the domestic insurance industry in the past has been affected by increasing losses on the motor portfolio besides the poor underwriting profitability of the domestic players, and their high level of management expenses because of heavy salary expenditure and the abundance of non-lucrative branches. Total value of the Indian insurance market (2004-05) is estimated at Rs. 450 billion. According to government sources, the insurance and banking services contribution to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) is 7% out of which the gross premium collection forms a significant part. However there has been gradual decrease in the market share witnessed by all the public insurers. In this context this paper attempts to analyse the performance of Public sector general insurance companies through earning and profitability.

The Literature Review

There are plenty of studies done on insurance in India and abroad. M. H Siddiqui, T. G. Sharma (2010) investigated that Liberalization of the financial services sector has led to insurance companies functioning increasingly under competitive pressures; so companies are consequently directing their strategies towards increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty through improved service quality. Kramer (1996) found a positive relationship between operating margin and financial solidity, that is, operating margin is negatively correlated to the rate of insolvency. K. Ravichandran, B. T. Mani, S. A. Kumar, S. Prabhakaran (2010) examined that the financial liberalization has led to intense competitive pressures and private banks dealing in retail banking are consequently directing their strategies towards increasing service quality level which fosters customer satisfaction and loyalty through improved service quality. According to Swiss Re (2004) important factors that determine the growth of the insurance business are the distribution of wealth, legal systems and property rights, the availability of insurance products, regulation and supervision, trust and risk awareness. Other non-economic factors have an impact on the development of insurance: religion, culture and education R. Mosahab, O. Mahamad, T. Ramayah, (2010) emphasised the service quality standard model has been used for evaluation of service quality. The results of this research show that in all aspects, customers' expectation, are higher than their perceptions of the Bank's operation, and in fact the quality of offered services is low.

Earning and Profitability Analysis of General Insurance Companies

Earnings are the key and arguably the only source of long term capital. Low profitability may signal fundamental problems of the insurer and may consider a leading indicator for solvency problems. Therefore, considerable attention is given to this area so that all indicators of earnings and profitability are included in this area. For non-life insurers, the ratio (net claims/net premium) is an important indicator of whether their pricing policy is correct, while the expense ratio (expenses/net premium) adds the aspect of operating costs into the analysis. It is important to note on technical detail; while the loss ratio has earned net premium into the denominator (and, on accrual basis, net claims are directly related to the denominator); the expense ratio is commonly defined with written net premium in the denominator (and again, the expenses other than claims are directly related to the denominator).

Then, the combined ratio, defined as the sum of the loss ratio and expense ratio, is a basic, commonly used measure of profitability (but note that it is not mathematically symmetric due to the different denominators). This indicator measures the performance of the underwriting operation but does not take into account the investment income. It is not uncommon to see combined ratios of over 100 percent and this may indicate that investment income is used as a factor in setting the premium rates. Prolonged triple-digit combined ratios, in an environment of low or volatile investment yields, signal a drain on capital and the prospect of solvency problems. Another indicator, investment income/net premium, focuses on the second major revenue source-investment income. Return on equity then indicates the overall level of profitability and return to shareholders.

In a fast growing highly populated nation to have a competitive and customer friendly insurance market, companies should be free to price their products. Consequently in India, the price deregulation has ignited intense competition in the insurance market and companies are marching towards more gaining more and more market without much thrust being laid on the prudential pricing. This has resulted in a situation, where the breakeven which was expected much earlier seem to be now pushed forward and in no case is expected in the coming three to four years. Here regulator IRDA has much to exercise given the juncture when insurance environment is marching towards free regime, any imperfection can erode customer faith which may be hazardous for the country like India.

Table 7 presents a detailed analysis of earnings and profitability of PSUs. The first ratio in the category of earnings and profitability is the ratio of net claims incurred to net premiums, termed as claim ratio and also known as loss ratio. This ratio represents the proportion of net claims incurred out of the earned premiums. As is evident from the analysis of the claim ratio, it is showing increasing trend for all the public sector insurers except United, where it has declined sharply. The low loss incurring ratio is good for financial health of the insurers, all the four PSUs under study seem to have high claim ratio and the ratio ranges between 84.96 & 102.43 percent, 87.64 & 99.69 percent, 78.62 & 93.09 percent and lastly 77.11 & 89 percent respectively for National, Oriental, United and New India respectively. It can be observed from the analysis of claim ratio that that up to 2006-07, ratio of New India, Oriental and United India insurers was by and large under a bit of control, but hereafter has witnessed sharp increase. It means that these companies were not able to put control on loss rate, perhaps because of poor risk management. However, surprisingly, United India was successful to manage the all time lowest claim ratio of 78.62 percent during 2008-09.

Expenses ratio in insurance parlance is the portion of premium used to pay all the costs of acquiring, writing and servicing insurance and reinsurance, the non-life insurance companies under study are seen to have been witnessing decreasing trend in this ratio which believed to be a good gesture for improving financial strength of the insurers. The expenses ratio recorded between 31.71 & 21.18 percent, 36.11 & 28.03 percent, 32.26 & 27.65 percent and 44.51 & 32.24 percent for New India, Oriental, National and United respectively (Table-1). The ratio witnessed minor fluctuations during the initial years of study; however as public sector insurers have done tremendous progress in controlling the expense ratio, which surely will have positive impact on the profitability picture.

Combined ratio, is a measure of profitability used by an insurance company to indicate how well it is performing in its daily operations. A ratio below 100 percent indicates that the company is making an underwriting profit, while as the ratio above 100 percent means that it is utilizing more money in paying claims and expenses that it receives from premiums. Combined ratio defined as the sum of loss ratio and expense ratio indicates how every rupee earned as premiums is spent. The claims ratio is claims owed as a percentage of revenue earned from premiums. The expense ratio is operating costs as a percentage of revenue earned from premiums. The combined ratio is calculated by taking the sum of incurred losses and expenses and then dividing them by earned premium. The combined ratio of the four PSUs has been exceptionally high indicating no possibility of operational profitability, the ratio has been worsening as the study progressed.

A combined ratio of 100 percent does not necessarily mean that the company is making losses, because this ratio is calculated after excluding the investment income. Higher returns on investment has always helped Indian general insurance companies offset underwriting losses, however, the routine has changed and there is a shift witnessed from interest or dividend income to profit from sale of investments and the trend is more pronounced among public sector insurers, which have reported strong returns by selling historical equity investments. However, declining stock prices substantially constrained investment returns of insurance companies; the profitability of the sector might decline. To report sustainable profits, insurance companies will need to generate income on their underwriting operations, instead of depending on investment returns.

The ratio presented in Table 7 ratio (4) represents the investment income ratio of the public sector insurers. The ratio indicates that there has been widespread decrease in the investment income for all insurance companies which can mainly be attributed to the global melt down and consequently higher volatility in the Indian financial market(IRDA 2008-09), the crises led to the deterioration in profitability due to loss on investments. The impact is clearly seen in the context of decrease in the investment income ratio, which ranges between 31.05 & 17.74 percent, 38.85 & 23.22 percent, 30.87 & 20.07 percent and 44.95 & 21.33 percent for New India, Oriental, National and United respectively. New India, Oriental and United seem to have been worst hit, where as National saw an upward trend in the initial years however it settled to a bit higher than initial year's ratio. This scenario also hints towards poor financial risk management on the part of companies.

Despite the significant underwriting losses, public sector general insurance companies have been profitable on account of their strong investment returns. The volatility in profits witnessed has been only because of dependence on income from investments and it has thus far been the lifesaving mechanism for the PSUs under study, consequently the regulator which has been ensuring insulation of companies from stock market shocks may not escape for more time. Simultaneously the support from investment side may not last longer due to the global crises therefore; efficiency in underwriting is very much felt to sustain in the competitive insurance environment.

The 5th ratio presented in table 7 represents the return on equity of the public sector insurers under study. Since return on equity (ROE) is the reward for the investors, the ratio seems to be decreasing over the period. In fact, the decreasing PAT has been attributed to the decrease in ratio, where as in case of National and Oriental, negative ROE has been as a result of overall losses incurred by the two companies. The fall would have been great if the PSUs have had the equity component more in the overall capital structure, however the investments and other assets base held by the company not only corrects the solvency surveillance but also the leaves the proportion for shareholders to rely upon. The situation however indicates drainage of resources, the strong capital foothold made prior to liberalization is being exploited to sustain in the competitive market. But now IRDA take steps to resolve the issue.

Table-1 Earnings and Profitability Analysis of public sector non life insurers(Figures in percent)

Companies		2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09
New India	1	77.113	88.134	80.342	86.824	89.000
	2	31.541	31.713	25.415	21.181	27.718
	3	108.654	119.847	105.757	108.005	116.718
	4	24.343	31.052	30.700	28.162	17.744
	5	268.155	358.190	729.976	700.564	112.075
Oriental	1	89.884	87.643	87.665	90.473	99.687
	2	34.377	36.113	28.030	28.635	29.817
	3	124.261	123.756	115.695	119.108	129.504
	4	38.847	34.911	31.002	27.857	23.215
	5	330.523	283.915	497.269	9.302	-52.660
National	1	84.962	102.431	86.510	94.047	99.162
	2	32.258	31.942	29.104	29.740	27.652
	3	117.22	134.373	115.614	123.787	126.814
	4	20.068	28.426	30.873	30.123	23.401
	5	131.125	-106.252	421.277	163.430	-149.210
United	1	92.411	93.093	90.259	92.753	78.617
	2	39.897	44.508	37.689	33.772	32.240
	3	132.308	137.601	127.948	126.525	110.857
	4	35.554	44.951	37.363	38.014	21.333
	5	307.711	425.230	352.574	421.083	317.367

Source: - Compiled from the Annual Reports of Insurance Companies

Note: 1. Loss Ratio = (Net Claims/Net Premiums)

2. Expense Ratio = (Expenses/Net Premiums)

3. Combined Ratio = Loss Ratio + Expense Ratio

4. Ratio of Investment Income to Net Premium

5. Return on Equity (ROE)

Liquidity

The frequency, severity and timing of insurance claims or benefits are uncertain, so insurers need to plan their liquidity carefully. Liquidity is usually a less pressing problem for insurance companies at least as compared to banks, since the liquidity of their liabilities is relatively predictable and for non life insurers the liabilities, besides claims are for shorter period of time. Further along with the link between illiquidity and insolvency, through the loss of confidence and runs, is less marked in insurance, a loss of confidence in an insurer nearly always causes policyholders to cancel over, demand a return of unexpired premium, and seek insurance elsewhere. Moreover the liquidity problem may call upon capital restructuring and infusion of more capital to heighten the liability graph.

Table-2 indicates the liquidity ratios of current assets to current liabilities. The ratio saw an increasing trend, except National insurance company as the study proceeds. The ratio lied between 46.45 & 68.80 percent, 32.37 & 47.87 percents, 38.95 & 43.56 percent and 27.40 and 35.52 percent respectively for New India, Oriental, National and United. National insurer, however, saw sharp increase in the current liabilities as a result the ratio witnessed a decrease in the later years.

Table-2: Liquidity of Public Sector Non Life Insurers (Figures in percent)

Companies	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09
New India	46.45	52.87	51.62	59.28	68.80
Oriental	32.37	33.33	42.04	39.27	47.87
National	43.56	38.95	39.42	37.40	39.26
United	27.40	32.93	30.75	31.88	35.52

Source: - Compiled from the Annual Reports of Insurance Companies

Note: Liquidity = Current Assets / Current Liability

Fig-1 Liquidity of Public Sector Non Life Insurers

The rule of thumb which usually is considered to be for liquidity is that it should be above 100 and more profoundly due to term nature of business of non life insurance, however given that the provisions kept aside as unexpired risk reserve the growing ratio does not seem to be worrying for the public sector insurers. The shorter tale nature of liabilities of non life sector of business also does not call upon the insurers to maintain the required ratio as per the general requirements, however, insurers may require more liquid funds to continue their solvent state and moreover the unforeseen claims call for the better liquidity position of the companies, which needs to be taken care of seriously.

Analyzing the financial performance of the insurers and it is observed that liberalization had a positive and promising impact on public sector insurance companies' performance especially on capital adequacy, management soundness and liquidity. It is concluded that though public sector insurers were continuously loosing market but still retained more than 59 percent of market share, the business has been increasing but not at the pace required to maintain the market share. The earnings and profitability had been affected and free market instincts continue to worsen the earnings. Whereas the assets base has been good throughout the study period, the underwriting losses seem to meet out of the investment income and profitable sale of earlier investments held. The negative impact is seen in the key

underwriting and investment side of the functioning. It is also important to note that public non life insurers have responded to the new challenges of competition, the same is reflected in the growing operational efficiency and expense ratios of the insurers. However underwriting profitability has been under strain and investment income which earlier stood to compensate losses, saw greater decrease and it is now not the interest or dividend income, which compensated the underwriting losses but the profitable sale of investments which are being employed to have PAT(Profit After Tax) in positive figures.

Conclusion

Despite the increasing business, the state owned insurers continued to lose the business which indicates that the public insurers could not keep pace with the increasing market. Figure representing the premium collection depict that despite the increasing premium collection, the market share of these companies declined to 59.41 percent from 79.93 percent. The management efficiency and soundness in fact is outcome of operational efficiency of the companies and in the light of this fact the study highlights that PSUs have recorded sound operational and management efficiency. In the present context the growing ratio of net premiums to gross premiums should be seen as encouraging phenomena, however due weightage be given to the technical reserves, which serve as shockers under the adverse selection. Since PSUs have strong technical reserve base, therefore, they have risk tolerance during the adverse selection of insurance business and this holds good because of growing retention ratio.

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